

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL CAPITAL, INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING AMONG IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between social capital, interpersonal communication skills, and psychological well-being among young adults. Social capital, encompassing trust, networks, and shared norms within social groups, significantly influences individual resources and social support systems. Interpersonal communication skills, crucial for forming and maintaining relationships, mediate the development and utilization of social capital. Psychological well-being, characterized by positive mental states, emotional stability, and life satisfaction, is often linked to these factors. The research examines how social capital and communication skills contribute to well-being, emphasizing their role in fostering resilience, coping mechanisms, and a sense of belonging. The data of the current study was collected from young adults through surveys to identify patterns and correlations. Findings reveal that higher levels of social capital and effective communication skills strongly predict better psychological well-being. These insights underline the importance of fostering interpersonal and social competencies in young adults to promote mental health and overall life. The number of participants included in this study was 300, Males=49, Females=251. The age of the students was 18-26 years old. The data were collected by using a convenience sampling techniques from Riphah International University, Faisalabad campus. The following scales /instruments were used to assess the findings. Demographic sheets, social capital scale, interpersonal communication skills scale and psychological wellbeing scale among young adults. Pearson Correlation, regression, Independent sample T-test were used to analyze the data that was collected from the students.

Keywords: Social capital, Interpersonal communication, Psychological wellbeing, Young adults.

INTRODUCTION

The ideas of social capital, interpersonal communication abilities, and psychological well-being are intricately linked and especially important when discussing young adults. According to Putnam (2000), social capital is the support and resources that people have access to through their social networks, including social ties that are bonded, bridged, and linked. These abilities help people successfully negotiate challenging social situations, strengthening bonds and lessening feelings of isolation and loneliness.

Social capital is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the resources available to individuals through their social networks (Putnam, 2000). It includes bonding social capital, which refers to close relationships with family and friends, and bridging social capital, which pertains to connections with broader social networks such as acquaintances and colleagues. High levels of social capital are associated with numerous benefits, including better health outcomes, increased civic

participation, and enhanced psychological well-being (Kawachi & Berkman, 2001).

Communication skills and social capital both affect psychological well-being, which is defined as self-acceptance, positive relationships, autonomy, and a sense of purpose in life (Ryff, 1989). Particularly among young adults, major life transitions like going to college or the workforce put their social resources and communication skills to the test (Arnett, 2000). Having good interpersonal skills can help them create networks of support, which reduces stress and improves wellbeing (Duck, 2007). Anxiety and sadness, on the other hand, can be made worse by a lack of social capital or inadequate communication abilities (Kawachi & Berkman, 2001). Studies highlight how these components work together in concert. Young adults who possess larger social capital and improved communication skills, for example, report higher psychological well-being because they are better able to handle interpersonal disagreements, ask for assistance when necessary, and uphold meaningful connections (Lin, 2001). Therefore, at this crucial developmental time, developing these networks and abilities help protect against mental health problems and improve general life happiness.

As young individuals move through developmental stages like getting a job or going to college, social capital is essential. According to research, social capital can affect mental health, employment opportunities, and academic achievement (Ellison et al., 2007). Psychological resilience, which is essential during the transition to maturity, is also influenced by social capital.

The strength and quality of social networks are influenced by interpersonal skills. Effective communicators are more likely to build connections based on cooperation, empathy, and trust (Baker & Watson, 2015). According to Putnam (2000), these abilities serve as a basis for developing bonding social capital, or relationships inside close-knit groups, and bridging social capital, or relationships between dissimilar groupings. Strong interpersonal communication abilities have been linked to improved access to and mobilization of support within networks,

according to research. Young adults with strong communication skills, for example, are better able to ask for assistance and guidance, which promotes mental health and lowers stress (Huang et al., 2014). Effective communication develops social capital by promoting trust and understanding between parties.

Communication skills act as a mediator in the link between psychological well-being and social capital. Studies indicate that individuals who effectively utilize social capital through communication experience reduced loneliness and enhanced life satisfaction (Williams, 2006). This interaction promotes a sense of belonging, purpose, and overall mental health.

Interest in a wider range of social determinants has grown since it seems that population mental health is not improving in tandem with economic factors (Donkin et al., 2018). It is well known that social factors at the neighborhood, school, and family levels can impact the potential of young individuals for future health, and that these potential negative effects must be minimized (Inchley et al., 2016).

It has been suggested that one shouldn't presume that social capital is conceptualized or impacts people in the same way in different situations or demographic groupings (Swann and Morgan, 2002). Since different facets of social capital may have varying effects on health outcomes for different age groups, we contend that it is reasonable to conduct a review and mapping exercise to summarize current understandings of social capital as it applies to young people. It could also help create a more comprehensive list of terminology.

It is challenging to synthesize the evidence supporting social capital as health-promoting phenomena because there are nearly as many approaches to defining and quantifying social capital as there are research papers. Similar to this, mental health is a multifaceted and intricate concept that is defined and assessed in a variety of ways in the literature. However, Morgan and Haglund contend that ignoring its ambiguities and complexity may prevent its theoretical foundation from being directly

translated into action (Morgan & Haglund, 2012).

According to Szreter and Woolcock (2004), social capital can be viewed in three different ways: bonding, bridging, and linking. Bonding social capital is defined as close-knit relationships within close-knit groups of friends or family, bridging social capital as connections among diverse social groups, and linking social capital as relationships with institutions or power structures. All of these forms of social capital support psychological wellbeing by providing a network of support, creating a sense of belonging, and making resources easier to access.

A common conceptualization of psychological wellbeing is subjective well-being, which includes both emotional and cognitive assessments of life. According to Ryff (1989), psychological wellbeing can be categorized into six factors: self-acceptance, positive relationships, personal growth, autonomy, environmental mastery, and purpose in life. Since the relational and communal components of social capital improve a person's sense of support, control, and social network integration, they have a special effect on the positive relationships, environmental mastery, and life purpose dimensions.

Social capital influences psychological wellbeing through several mechanisms. First, social support is a primary component, as it provides individuals with resources to cope with life stressors, thus reducing the likelihood of negative mental health outcomes. Socially supported individuals tend to report higher life satisfaction and lower levels of psychological distress, as they have reliable outlets for emotional support and advice (Lin, 2001).

Furthermore, social capital aids in the development of emotional resilience. Being part of a supportive network enables individuals to navigate life's challenges more effectively, as they have access to shared knowledge, emotional support, and material assistance. For instance, a study by Cacioppo and Hawkey (2009) found that individuals with strong social connections were better equipped to handle stress and exhibited lower levels of psychological distress. Similarly, De Silva et al. (2005) showed that community-

level social capital was associated with lower levels of depression and anxiety among residents, emphasizing the importance of social cohesion in promoting mental health.

The relationship between social capital, interpersonal communication skills, and psychological well-being among young adults is interactive and mutually reinforcing. Social capital and communication skills work in tandem, as social networks provide opportunities for social interaction, and strong interpersonal skills enhance the quality of these interactions. Social capital can improve psychological well-being by creating networks that facilitate emotional and instrumental support, while interpersonal communication skills enable individuals to effectively leverage this support (Song et al., 2010). For example, young adults with high levels of social capital and strong communication skills are more likely to seek out social support, engage in meaningful conversations, and build trusting relationships, which protect against feelings of isolation and promote well-being (Segrin & Taylor, 2007).

In Pakistan, researchers are paying more and more attention to how social capital and communication abilities affect the wellbeing of young adults. Social support networks, such as family, friends, and community ties, are crucial for reducing stress and fostering mental health in Pakistan due to its collectivistic culture (Rehman et al., 2022). However, interpersonal communication patterns have changed in response to globalization and developments in digital communication, which has an impact on how young adults interact with their social contexts (Hussain & Riaz, 2021). Therefore, building focused interventions and policies that improve mental health outcomes requires an understanding of how social capital, communication abilities, and psychological well-being interact among Pakistani young adults.

Numerous elements, such as coping strategies, self-esteem, and social support, affect young adults' psychological well-being (Suhail & Chaudhry, 2004). Although there has been a recent surge in mental health awareness in Pakistan, the stigma associated with

psychological problems still prevents many people from getting professional assistance (Rehman et al., 2022). According to research, social support networks play a major role in young people's resistance against stress, anxiety, and depression (Sadia et al., 2018). Additionally, efficient communication improves emotional expressiveness, which lessens psychological distress and feelings of loneliness (Malik & Rafique, 2021). Designing mental health interventions that are suited to the sociocultural circumstances of Pakistani youth requires an understanding of these processes.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The relationship between social capital, interpersonal communication skills, and psychological well-being is a well-researched area in social sciences, with significant implications for the mental health of young adults. This literature review examines the interconnections among these constructs and explores how they collectively influence psychological well-being. It is essential to comprehend the connection between psychological well-being, interpersonal communication abilities, and social capital in order to create strategies that effectively support young adults' mental health.

The literature highlights the importance of social networks and communication skills in fostering psychological well-being and suggests practical approaches for enhancing these elements. Future research should continue to explore these interconnections and develop interventions that leverage social capital and communication skills to support mental health of young adults.

1.5 Research Questions

The research questions under investigation are being stated in this section.

1. What is the link of social capital, interpersonal communication skills and psychological wellbeing among young adults?
2. What is direction and magnitude of the effect of interpersonal communication skills on the psychological well-being of a young adult?

3. Based on the empirical evidence, how is psychological well-being being affected by the social capital?

1.6 Research Objectives

The goal of this study was to investigate the relationship between social capital, psychological well-being, and interpersonal communication skills in University students.

- To find out the association between social capital, interpersonal communication skills and psychological wellbeing among young adults.
- To predict the relationship between social capital, interpersonal communication skills and psychological wellbeing.
- To find out the variation on the bases of gender differences between social capital, interpersonal communication skills and psychological wellbeing among young adults.

Research Hypothesis

- Interpersonal Communication Skills and Social Capital would be strong predictor of Psychological well being in University students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter described the methodological strategy that was employed in the next chapter. The following methodology section provided a detailed discussion of data targeting, selection, collection, and analysis. It also included information on the study's location, participants, ethical considerations, statistical analysis, and a summary of the measures used. Every term used in the study was explained, and before delving deeper into the specifics of the approaches employed at each stage of the investigation, all necessary topics were addressed. G*Power software were used for sample size calculation, which was essential for obtaining reliable and generalizable results.

3.1 Research Design

A correlation design is used in this research to examine the relationship between social capital, interpersonal communication skills, and psychological well-being among young adults. Study designs that investigate the connection between two or more variables include correlation studies.

3.2 Sampling Techniques

The convenience sampling method was used to collect the data. The sample size was 300 students.

3.3 Participants of Study

A total sample of 300 participants will be selected. Due to the nature of the current study, a convenient sample of adults will be taken from senior students of the leading institutions in Faisalabad who are pursuing their BS and MS degrees. These individuals will be requested to fill out the questionnaire provided in the Appendix under the guidance of the researcher. The cooperation of the participants will be acknowledged through the presentation of a letter of appreciation to each participant. Regarding the sampling design, the sample size will be determined based on the recommendations of leading researchers, considering the statistical techniques used for the analysis. The relevant sources will also be cited not only in the text but also in the reference list.

3.4 Inclusion Criteria

- All the young adult students who were able to **respond** were **part** of the current study.
- The study included students who were **studying** at Riphah University, Faisalabad Campus.
- The study included both married and unmarried participants.
- Participants' family types, both nuclear and joint, were represented in the sample.
- Participants' locations, both urban and rural, were included.

3.5 Exclusion Criteria

- Participants were excluded if they were unable to understand the data, paper, and forms, and provide their informed consent.
- Participants who were thought to be intoxicated at the time the data were gathered were also not included in the study.
- To safeguard the study from any potential negative effects that the participants' physical and mental impairments might have, such individuals were either excluded from the study or did not participate in it.

• Rapport and Trust of Participants

In order for researchers to conduct successful research, it is important to establish trust and maintain a good rapport between the researcher and the participants. Therefore, before beginning data collection, it was necessary to build a strong rapport with the participants. The researcher introduced the participants in the evaluation settings and explained the purpose and objectives of the study. Additionally, the researcher assured the participants that the psychological test results would remain confidential. Throughout the testing process, the researcher clarified and addressed all participant concerns and questions in a positive and simplified manner. The participants were also informed that they would receive any necessary information.

3.7 Ethical Consideration

Every safety measure was taken before the study was prepared and during its execution. Before the study's topic was approved by the Board of Study (BOS) and the Board of Advanced Study and Research (BASR), it was first approved by the psychology department's research board. This allowed the author to properly investigate the topic. The study was conducted in a manner that ensured the dignity and respect of the respondents was maintained. The researcher ensured that the participants' rights and welfare were upheld. The purpose of the study and its confidentiality policies were explained to the participants. The volunteers were also informed that they would not receive any compensation for their participation.

3.8 Instruments

These instruments are used here to assess social capital, interpersonal communication Skills and psychological well-being.

3.8.1 Demographic Sheet

To collect personal information, the examiner prepared a demographic information form that includes the following: Name, Email, Age, Gender, Marital Status, Location, Family Type, and Education Program.

3.8.2 Social Capital Questionnaires

According to Wang et al. (2014), social capital refers to the accumulation of resources within social networks that individuals can use to achieve various goals. The Social Capital Scale consists of 16 items and is available in English. This scale has two subscales: bonding and bridging. Items 1 to 8 belong to the bonding subscale, while items 9 to 16 belong to the bridging subscale. The response scale for participants' ratings of their response size is as follows: 1 (a few), 2 (less than average), 3 (average), 4 (more than average), and 5 (a lot). The Social Capital Questionnaire, developed by Wang and colleagues, evaluates various aspects of social capital, including its relational, structural, and cognitive components. It measures the quality and extent of individuals' social networks, trust, shared norms, and mutual obligations all of which are essential for fostering cooperation, knowledge exchange, and overall well-being.

3.8.3 Interpersonal Communication Skills Scale

Bienvenu (1971) created the Interpersonal Communication Skills Questionnaire to evaluate people's capacity for meaningful and successful communication in various social and private settings. This scale is available in English. It consists of **40 items** related to interpersonal communication, with three response options: (1) **Usually = Yes**, (2) **Seldom = No**, and (3) **Sometimes**. If a question describes behavior that occurs frequently or typically, the "Yes" column should be selected. If the behavior occurs rarely or never, the "No" column should be chosen. If you are unable to decide between "Yes" or "No," you should mark the "Sometimes" option. The **Interpersonal Communication Inventory** comprises five components.

Psychological Wellbeing (Ryff, 2010)

The scale measures psychological wellness levels and consists of a total of 18 items, each with seven response options. The response options are as follows: one=strongly agree, two=somewhat agree, three=a little agree, four=disagree, five=a little disagree, six=somewhat disagree, and seven=strongly

disagree. The scale is designed to measure six dimensions of psychological wellness.

Research Setting

"In addition to gathering data in a managed and impartial way, important techniques were used. The context for the assessment of the measures was based on expert evaluation. Under these circumstances, a great deal of effort was made to prevent any type of disruption. The procedure for administration was adhered to and remained consistent in all cases. The management medium remained constant throughout all instances. Guidelines and protocols were strictly followed, as stated in the instructions for procedures."

Research Site

The current study was conducted at Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus, with young adults who are pursuing their education. The study included both married and unmarried individuals, as well as males and females.

Procedure

A crucial phase in research is data collection, which entails systematic techniques to gather information relevant to the study's objectives. The process begins with selecting appropriate methods, such as surveys, interviews, observations, or experiments, and determining whether qualitative, quantitative, or mixed data is required. While focus groups and interviews provide in-depth qualitative insights, surveys often use structured questionnaires to collect large amounts of quantitative data. Experiments manipulate variables to examine cause-and-effect relationships, whereas observational techniques record behaviors or occurrences in their natural settings. Once the techniques are selected, researchers develop tools, test their reliability through pilot studies, and make any necessary adjustments. Throughout the process, ethical considerations, such as obtaining informed consent and ensuring confidentiality, remain crucial. After data collection, the information is systematically organized and prepared for analysis to generate meaningful insights aligned with the study's objectives.

Analytical Statistics

Following the scoring of each metric in accordance with the guidelines in the manual, a Microsoft Excel sheet was created. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, Version 27) was used to analyze the results. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to the full sample. Techniques such as t-test analysis, linear regression, and Pearson correlation for random samples were employed to compute the data and test the hypotheses.

Data Analysis

Data management and analysis procedures in this study will adhere to established standards mentioned in the literature. The collected data will be stored electronically using SPSS data files. After verifying the of assumptions, statistical analysis and modeling will be conducted using two widely used software tools: SPSS and AMOS. Descriptive analysis will be incorporated as an integral part of the study. Inferential analysis will be performed to determine whether the effects, differences, and relationships are statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A range of questionnaires were utilized to gather information from male and female young adults enrolled at the Riphah International University Faisalabad Campus in order to evaluate their psychological wellness, interpersonal communication skills, and social capital. Descriptive inferential statistics were computed and SPSS 26 was utilized to evaluate the data. The following tables offer thorough additional information to clarify data-related concepts: frequency, descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, correlation, regression, and T-test.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Participants (N=300).

Variables	N	%	Cumulative
Gender			
Female	251	83.7	100.0
Male	49	16.3	16.3
Marital Status	38		12.7
Married	262	12.7	100.0
Unmarried		87.3	
Location			
Urban	208	69.3	69.3
Rural	92	30.7	100.0
Family Type			
Nuclear	196	65.3	65.3
Combine	104	34.7	100.0
Program			
BS	175	58.3	58.3
Mphil	125	41.7	100.0

Table 1 Shows that the frequency and percentage of participants according to program, location, family type, gender, and marital status. 49 men (16.3%) and 251 women (83.7%) make up the gender gap. There are 262 unmarried people (87.3%) and

38 married people (12.7%). The locations are 92 Rural (30.7%) and 208 Urban (69.3%). 196 Nuclear (65.3%) and 104 Combine (37.7%) are the family types. 125 MPhil (41.7%) and 175 BS (58.3%) make up the program.

Table 2 :Descriptive Statistic between Social Capital Interpersonal Communication Skills and Psychological Wellbeing among Young Adults (N=300).

Variables	M	S.D	Skewness	Kurtosis
Social Capital	2.49	.64	.20	-.13
Interpersonal Communication Skills	2.09	.18	.00	-.28
Psychological Wellbeing	3.59	.68	.10	-.33

Table 2 Shows that the statistical characteristic of Social Capital , Interpersonal communication Skills and Psychological Wellbeing among young adults. The Mean of Social Capital is 2.4927

and S.D is .64691 The Means of Interpersonal communication skills is 2.0999 and S.D is .18341. The Means of Psychological Wellbeing is 3.5969 and S.D is .68069.

Table 3:Reliability Scales Analysis between Social Capital Interpersonal Communication Skills and Psychological Wellbeing among Young Adults (N=300).

Variables	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Social Capital	16	.80
Interpersonal Communication Skills	40	.56
Psychological Wellbeing	18	.80

Table 3 Shows that the reliability of the variables are there Social Capital Scale Consist 16 items to measures it and Cronbach's alpha of .808 indicates good internal consistency. Interpersonal Communication Skills have 40 items and the Cronbach's alpha value is .565 is Questionable and acceptable internal consistency.

Psychological wellbeing consist 18 items and 6 subscales and Cronbach's alpha .806 and .81 indicates Good internal consistency. All three measures have high internal consistency, according to the reliability study, which makes them trustworthy tools for assessing Social Capital, Interpersonal communication Skills and Psychological Wellbeing in the sample of 300 participants.

Table 5 :Summary of linier Regression with Social Capital Interpersonal Communication Skills and Psychological Wellbeing among Young Adults (N=300).

Variables	R	R ²	Std.Error	F	Sig
	0.94	0.89	0.22	1271.79	0.000
Model	Un.Std.B	Std.Error	Std.B	T	Sig
(Constant)	-1.07	0.16		-6.69	0.00
SC	1.06	0.07	0.28	15.16	0.00
IC	0.97	.02	0.93	49.35	0.00

Table 5 Shows that social capital interpersonal communication skills are independent. The effect of social capital on psychological wellbeing is significant (p= 0.00).Table 5 also shows that the coefficient of determinations 0.89 which means 89.5% in psychological wellbeing is explained by social capital and interpersonal communication skills. Rest of the 10.5% variation is explained by independent variable not included in the model. This table also shows that the overall model is significant and the strongest

predictor is interpersonal communication skills followed by the social capital.

Discussion

Particularly for young adults, social capital, interpersonal communication abilities, and psychological well-being are intimately related. Bourdieu (1986) and Coleman (1988) popularized the term "social capital," which describes the networks, norms, and trust that promote collaboration and reciprocal gain in a society. Social capital among young adults frequently takes the form of peer groups,

friendships, and online communities. Because strong social networks provide emotional support and a sense of belonging, research shows that higher levels of social capital are linked to improved psychological well-being (Putnam, 2000). Conversely, inadequate communication abilities might impede the formation of significant relationships, which could result in emotions of loneliness and isolation. These emotions have been linked to negative mental health consequences, such as anxiety and sadness (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018). Furthermore, conversations concerning the effects of technology-mediated communication on interpersonal skills and psychological well-being have been sparked by young adults' growing reliance on digital communication platforms. While some research suggests that digital connections can enhance in-person communication, other studies point to possible drawbacks such as diminished empathy and heightened social comparison (Twenge et al., 2018).

The concept of psychological well-being includes aspects like autonomy, personal development, life purpose, and positive relationships (Ryff, 1989). Young adults who have strong interpersonal skills and strong social networks are more likely to report psychological well-being; for example, having supportive family relationships and close friends has been shown to reduce the effects of stress and promote resilience (Cohen & Wills, 1985); on the other hand, social disconnection or perceived inadequacies in communication skills can lead to negative emotional states and lower life satisfaction; and interventions that focus on improving interpersonal communication, such as counseling or training programs, have been successful in increasing social capital and promoting psychological well-being in this population (Segrin, 2001). Socio cultural elements like community norms, financial standing, and resource accessibility also have an impact on the relationship among social capital, communication abilities, and well-being. It may be difficult for young adults from underprivileged backgrounds to create social capital because they have less access to networks of support or chances to learn new skills. A comprehensive strategy that blends

individual-level therapies with larger societal activities to promote inclusive and supportive environments is needed to address these inequities (Lin, 2001).

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.4 Recommendations

Recommendations in terms of Implications and Limitations are being listed in the following sub-sections.

- Keeping in view the presence of a reasonable proportion of young population in the country it is important to consider that the present study can be extended in future in different contexts and scenarios.

5.4.1 Implications

- The present study will highlight the importance of Social Capital and Interpersonal Communication to improve the Psychological Well-being of the young adults.
- To broaden the scope of the study few other related variables e.g. Eustress, Cognition, and Resilience etc. may be included to investigate their collective and isolated effect on the Psychological Well-being of the students.

According to Hersberger (2013) resilience is a sort of defense mechanism of a university student while facing the stressful consequences on the campus like the lack of support and effective teaching style on the part of the teacher, work burden, huge class size, longer working hours, bullying by the students and the teachers, financial hardships, lack of sleep, relationship breakup, tough evaluation system, lack of confidence due to limited digital literacy, fatigue, social isolation, difficulty of course material, lack of psychological well-being, health issues, low emotional intelligence, part-time job, competition, bad connections, defeat, abuse, inflation, weaker relationships, fear, uncertainty, and procrastination. Concepts of stress, resilience, social support, and cognition collectively serve the students to buffer from unfavorable events on or off the campus.

Eustress can be defined in a number of ways including "Response to a stressor in terms of positive psychology". It is an indicator of the presence of positive psychology states in an

individual and promotes well-being and quality of life, and the work of higher education professor as well as professionals (Fonseca and Jordao, 2019).

Shi and Qu (2021) underline the importance of creating cognitive capabilities in the students due to the fact that it predicts the academic performance positively and significantly under the mediating role personality characteristics and psychological health. Cognition shapes behavior, thoughts and emotions. Hence teachers can play an important role in this regard to enhance the students' learning and the classroom environment (Vandenbroucke, 2017).

5.4.2 Limitations

Like every study the present study is subject to some limitations in terms of generalizability, measurement bias and selection bias, cause and effect relationship, and extraneous factors. Findings of this study are generalizable to the population of male =49 and female= 251 students from which the sample was taken i.e. Riphah International University, Faisalabad Campus. This was due to limitations of resources and time. If funding is available a greater project can be conducted on the part of University administration, some NGO or a National Organization like HEC to enhance the psychological well-being of the students and young adults at large which are an asset of Pakistan.

Use of more effective and advanced measurement tools and the use more appropriate probability sampling design may lead to the reduction of bias subject to the condition that more suitable data collections methods may be incorporated with all respects.

It is a well-known fact that the techniques of correlation and regression are observational techniques and do not lead to the cause and effect relationships. To establish cause-and-effect relationships experimental studies are required to be employed which demand control on the independent variables and hence are more complex and difficult to implement in terms of resources.

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